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THE CLUSTERIZATION ALGORITHM AS A FACTOR OF THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE REGIONS OF UKRAINE

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Анотація

В статті розглянути питання розробки алгоритму кластеризації з метою оцінки конкурентоспроможності регіону. Визначено особливості кластеризації та систематизації впливу кластерів на регіональну конкурентоспроможність. Визначено, що конкурентоспроможність регіону залежить від креативного потенціалу, який взаємозв'язаний з креативними кластерами. Розглянута методика побудови кластерних об'єднань перегукується з класифікацією кластерів в залежності від етапу його побудови: прекластер, або агломерат, кластер, що зароджується, кластер, що розвивається, зрілий кластер, кластер, що трансформується.

Abstract

The article considers the issue of developing a clustering algorithm for the purpose of assessing the competitiveness of the region. The peculiarities of clustering and systematization of the influence of clusters on regional competitiveness are determined. It was determined that the competitiveness of the region depends on the creative potential, which is interconnected with creative clusters. The considered method of building cluster associations echoes the classification of clusters depending on the stage of its construction: precluster, or agglomerate, nascent cluster, developing cluster, mature cluster, transforming cluster.

Ключові слова: кластер, регіон, конкурентоспроможність, фактор.

Keywords: cluster, region, competitiveness, factor.

Scientific studies have proven, and practical experience has confirmed, that the cluster is an element of the system of regional competitiveness, which is responsible for the pace and qualitative content of regional development. One of the first A. Marshall in his work "Principles of Economic Theory" investigated that territorially united enterprises engaged in family activities receive additional positive advantages and opportunities, for example, a common base of professionals, access to highly specialized suppliers, information exchange, options for combining investment activities [10].

An important consequence of cluster formation is the formation of synergistic effects aimed at regional development:

First, the cluster acts as a community of enterprises or closely related industries that mutually contribute to the growth of each other's competitiveness.

Secondly, for the economy of the region, the cluster plays the role of points of internal growth and the function of a platform for external expansion.

Thirdly, clustering causes a chain effect, creating a precedent for rational territorial cooperation and thereby serves as an impetus for the formation of new clusters [3].

Cluster participants receive additional competitive advantages as a result of the effect of scale, coverage and synergy of the multiple effect, which is obtained as a result of merging individual parts into a single system. Clusters are distinguished by a stable partnership of interdependent economic and legal agents, a combination of cooperation and competition, the effects of knowledge spillover, an increase in cash flow due to the unification of the flows of enterprises that are members of the cluster, shared use of infrastructure, a reduction in transport costs, i.e. advantages that provide opportunities for the cluster to obtain a potential that exceeds the sum of the potentials of individual cluster participants [7].

Clusters attract foreign and domestic investments to the region, which leads to the growth of business activity, which turns into "concrete advantages of nations", in which the advantages of individual territories and regions come to the fore. Clusters form and group the demand for products of regional production, which in turn determines the emergence of services and structures that provide specialized services related to the consumption of manufactured products. Clusters provide an opportunity for open membership in regional economic systems to business entities from other regions that are trying to develop regional markets. Clusters create a unique social environment based on the values of humanism and human dignity, free enterprise and social security. According to the authors, the social environment encourages the education of qualitatively new members of society who adhere to the principles of openness of regional economies. Clusters generate the scientific and technical potential of the region in a form that allows to eliminate the gap between science and production, to involve universities, research institutes, scientific centers, etc. in the field of production. Clusters strengthen cooperative ties between deeply

specialized production structures, scientific and technical institutes, financial and credit institutions, commercial and consulting organizations, and also create conditions for the formation and principles of development of a competitive market environment, where there are no monopolistic structures and the spirit of entrepreneurship dominates, which makes the region is attractive as an object of economic activity [4].

The prerequisites for the formation of clusters can be considered the presence of potential and managerial competences. The regional potential of cluster formation includes such components as scientific, resource, innovative, and institutional. Scientific potential plays a decisive role in the formation of innovation clusters. But its presence is an additional incentive for the development of traditional industries as well, which, using scientific achievements and having the possibility of their practical application, get additional competitive advantages.

Resource potential is considered as a set of resource reserves, sources, means that can be involved in the production and provision of services in the region with a certain development of productive forces in the context of the implementation of specific goals.

Innovative potential adjusts the resource potential in relation to the ability of the economic system to implement innovations. Innovative potential includes personnel, technological, marketing and other components. It is the innovative potential that ensures the strategic development of the region, increases its attractiveness for various types of consumers of regional services.

Infrastructural potential is the ability of regional infrastructure to meet the needs of regional production.

It is believed that the innovation cluster provides an opportunity to use the advantages of two ways of coordinating economic systems: intra-firm hierarchy and market mechanism. This allows for quick and efficient dissemination of new knowledge; concentrate on business processes that provide the greatest added value by using the advantages of outsourcing; effectively attract and use investments [8].

The competitiveness of the region, as evidenced by the materials of foreign and domestic studies, depends on the creative potential, which is interconnected with creative clusters. Clusters consisting of creative enterprises require a greater number of components for functioning and development than industrial ones, on the basis of which business parks focused on various technological processes can be laid. It is believed that creative clusters can include non-profit organizations, cultural institutions, stage venues, design workshops, studios of individual masters, science parks, media centers [5,6].

Creative approaches are used by all industrially developed countries, which can serve as an incentive for the regions of Ukraine to emphasize the development of a strategy for the development of creativity and its individual tools, the formation of a coordinated and balanced list of measures to support talents, the implementation of creative ideas on regional soil, and the development of folk traditions. At the same time, not forgetting the need for targeted analytical studies [9].

The implementation of innovation clusters necessitates taking into account the following features of innovation:

1. Innovation is a commercial concept, not a technological and intellectual property concept. As an economic concept, innovation is aimed at obtaining profit, which is the basis for the further formation of competitive advantages. An innovation that does not lead to economic benefits cannot be involved in the process of clustering the economy.

2. Innovation has certain gradations. As a result of the innovation process, a completely new idea for a product or service can be developed, and existing products can also be improved. This approach makes it possible to single out radical and gradual innovations.

3. Regardless of the degree of innovation, the reasons for its occurrence lie in the exchange of knowledge and information between employees united in a team.

4. As a rule, the source of innovation is not an individual or a company unrelated to others, but a group of people or companies that have joined forces when working on an innovative project [8].

Scientists identify five stages of cluster formation. This is campaigning and motivation of potential project participants, development of a general strategy, pilot project, strategic project and self-regulation stage [1]. At the first stage, it is proposed to identify a "critical mass" of small and medium-sized enterprises that have common problems in business; help them to understand the advantages of the cluster; to form a group of supporters of the cluster association. The result of actions at this stage is the formation of a group of businessmen, and, accordingly, their enterprises, who have understood the value of cluster formation and are capable of joint activities. At the second stage, the development of the cluster strategy takes place, which, according to the authors, includes an analysis of common problems and opportunities, the formation of a joint action plan and the structure of the relationships of the enterprises included in the cluster. The stage ends with the definition of legal status and formulation of internal organizational principles. The pilot project stage aims to test the technology of interaction within the cluster, the successful results of which prove the effectiveness of the idea of unification and provide further stimulation of participants in joint business activity. Completion of this stage provides an opportunity to move to the stage of developing projects of a strategic nature, which, according to the authors, consists in achieving the necessary level of specialization and division of labor in the cluster, combining resources, introducing the latest technologies, creating new enterprises, etc. The final stage involves the independent activity of the cluster, the introduction of self-regulation and self-coordination functions.

The considered method of building cluster associations echoes the classification of clusters depending on the stage of its construction:

- precluster or agglomerate;
- nascent cluster;
- a developing cluster;
- mature cluster;
- a transforming cluster [9].

Clustering of the regional economy can be carried out according to such an algorithm.

1. Definition of the mission of the cluster, its main tasks that ensure its viability and efficiency.

2. Conducting a strategic analysis, which will allow to assess the external environment and identify signals that contain internal threats to the cluster, as well as its strengths.

3. Framing the organizational contour of the cluster, outlining the circle of enterprises and organizations that are potentially interested in the formation of the cluster, as well as their unification will contribute to regional development.

4. Develop a strategy for the cluster, which includes all stages of its life cycle.

5. Determine the basics of cluster regional policy.

6. To design a system of regional controlling for the activities of the cluster, the purpose of which is to coordinate efforts at the regional level, which will create conditions for the further development of the cluster.

7. Formulate regional institutional conditions for the successful functioning of the cluster based on institutional design.

8. Form the cluster and ensure its successful functioning.

Each of these stages contains a huge semantic and functional load and affects the result of the clustering process to the full extent. This means that poor execution of the algorithmic iteration leads to errors when moving to the next stage and causes a chain of erroneous decisions. Based on this, the mission of the cluster accumulates great potential, defines not only the perspective, the orientation of the existence of the entire cluster, but also the means by which these orientations will be implemented. The mission is understood in broad and narrow meanings. In a broad sense, the mission is a statement of the organization's philosophy, purpose, meaning of existence and defines the values, principles, ideologies, according to which the economic system intends to carry out its activities [4, p. 35].

In a narrow sense, the mission concentrates the strategic goals of the organization, shows what the enterprise will direct its activities towards.

Strategic analysis of a region or regional cluster is manifested in the procedure of searching and selecting strategic alternatives for the development of the socio-economic system, the most stable patterns and trends capable of playing a decisive role in the future and forecasting performance indicators based on them [4, p. 41]. Practical analytics uses PEST-analysis, which is aimed at studying macroenvironmental factors, but this method does not provide complete information when creating a cluster.

When forming a cluster, first of all, a SWOT analysis is carried out, which allows to highlight the advantages and disadvantages of the organization's goals and threats or positive factors of the external environment. SWOT analysis allows you to identify and outline the main priorities, problems and opportunities that arise in the environment of the functioning of the socio-economic system, and which can affect the results of the cluster's activities.

In the strategic analysis of the clustering of the regional economy, the subject of strategic analysis pays special attention to the information base, especially regarding the usefulness of information that meets, from the perspective of the SWOT analysis team, the following criteria: timeliness, i.e. the ability to obtain data in a specific period of time to satisfy the needs of the analytical group and conduct an analysis adequate to the conditions; reliability - a guarantee of objectivity and truthfulness of data, which determines the possibility of making realistic management decisions; sufficiency for objective consideration of all factors that ensure the effective implementation of the cluster system of the regional economy; reliability – provision of information from reliable sources, which minimizes the possibility of analytical and, as a result, management errors; addressability – receiving information by analysts who use it; legal correctness – compliance of information, especially of a strategic nature, with regulatory and legislative acts; multiplicity of information – repeated use of data in the analysis process; the speed of information processing – ensuring the timeliness of obtaining the results of certain stages of the analysis; relevance - compliance with the current realities of the state of the regional economy and the trend of its changes; comparability - the ability to compare data from different regions for different periods of time [11, p. 39-40].

The third stage of regional economy clustering consists in framing the organizational outline of the future cluster. The effectiveness of the cluster depends on the organizational factors that primarily determine the presence of certain members of the cluster.

Thus, the framing of the cluster, or its organizational contour, involves determining the optimal composition of the enterprises of the basic industry, which make up the core of the cluster, and enterprises - suppliers of raw materials and material resources, information, innovations, labor force, as well as organizations that provide various types of services: from risk management services to financial support services.

The following recommendations can be offered to the regional authorities:

a) adjustment of the regional development strategy taking into account the cluster orientation of economic sector reorganization as a factor of regional competitiveness;

b) to institutionalize clusters as a system of interaction norms between business subjects, subjects of regional administration, subjects of production, scientific and social infrastructure in the region. In other words, there is a need in the region for the formation of a modern culture of mutual relations between entrepreneurs;

c) create a system of regional controlling for strategic management of regional competitiveness, which will also cover issues of viability and efficiency of clusters.

Controlling as a function of strategic management will allow to create a system of "planning - monitoring

of the implementation of strategic management - analysis of the results of strategic management of the competitiveness of the Transcarpathian region."

The proposed regional economic system clustering algorithm will be effective in reorganizing the regional management structure according to the matrix scheme.

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